

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

CURRENT ISSUES OF TEACHING PHYSICS IN ENGLISH IN KAZAKH PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract

The article discusses the provisions for teaching physical disciplines in Kazakh universities in English. In this regard, some opinions and wishes were expressed regarding the trilingual project. When forming separate groups studying physical subjects in English, attention was paid to the following provisions. The first is students who graduated from schools in the Kazakh language and have an appropriate level in English. And the second - exactly the same situation, but graduated from school in the Russian language. The third is students who studied physical disciplines at school in English and have relatively good preparation in this direction. The corresponding methodological proposals for teaching physical disciplines in English are proposed, taking into account the indicated provisions. These proposals are made on the basis of the experience gained in this direction in the course of work at the Abai Kazakh National Pedagogical University.

Keywords: *physical disciplines; English language; methodology; opinions; suggestions; textbooks; students.*

Earlier, in order to increase the competitiveness of the country and citizens, a phased implementation of the cultural project "Trinity of Languages" was proposed. In accordance with this project, the issue of the development of three languages in the republic was envisaged: Kazakh, English and Russian [1].

In the context of the rapid development of modern science and education, the teaching of natural sciences on the basis of fundamental sciences in international English will certainly be of great importance.

About four or five years ago, proposals for a mass transition to teaching natural sciences in English in schools and universities of the country, in particular physics, computer science, chemistry, were somewhat hasty and not deeply studied. These are probably the main reasons why these proposals have not yet been implemented in the country's education system.

Thirdly, if we look at history, there is a danger that the painstaking work of our intelligentsia, which has worked hard for decades and even hundreds of years to teach natural disciplines in the Kazakh language, will be wasted.

Fourth, this is even the main reason. Violation of the right of the country's youth to study these subjects in any language. It should be noted that there are other objective and subjective reasons for this problem.

Therefore, the responsible persons of the country have recently come to a calm and balanced decision on this issue. In other words, they support the teaching of these disciplines in English not everywhere, but in special schools and individual groups of universities. Here we would like to say a few words about trilingualism. Attempts to implement this project from kindergarten and elementary school can lead to the emergence of an illiterate generation, weakly speaking three languages.

In accordance with the basic principles of nature, medicine and pedagogy, our children should learn other

languages only after studying the surrounding world and society in their native language, i.e. Kazakh. Therefore, we believe that our children should study only in their own language, that is, Kazakh, at least from kindergarten to the fifth grade, and only then start learning other languages. In this regard, for example, we can follow the example of Japan, which is recognized as a civilized advanced country.

Now let's move on to the main issues of the article. In recent years, the Kazakh National Pedagogical University named after Abai has been successfully teaching natural sciences in English in separate special groups. Now let's briefly focus on our methodological experience with the problems that arise when teaching physics in English in separate groups studying at the Institute of Mathematics, Physics and Computer Science of our university. When forming a group of students studying these disciplines in English, the following cases were observed.

The first case is students who graduated from school in Kazakh, studied English well at the school level, and now want to develop it in connection with their specialty.

The second case is students of the same level as mentioned in the first case, but who graduated from school in Russian.

The third case is students who have studied natural sciences in English in special schools and are better prepared than in previous cases.

The fourth case is students who graduated from school in Kazakh or Russian, but have skills in other specialties than in natural specialties and have a poor command of English.

If we want to achieve good results in this area, it is better to create separate small groups and develop

special programs for them, taking into account the specifics of the situation. In this situation, there are no such opportunities, so they all study in the same group.

Experience shows that in one group it is necessary to work with students of different levels in English, and with language peculiarities, depending on graduate schools in physical disciplines, according to different methodological approaches during classes.

For example, in the first case mentioned above, it is effective for students to familiarize themselves with the topic first through appropriate textbooks in Kazakh, translate its definitions, theories and equations into English, and then study and analyze using appropriate textbooks in English.

In the second case, it is better for students to do the same, of course it is clear that they will use the appropriate textbooks in English and Russian.

The need to use these methods for students in the first and second cases in the group is that they first think about the studied physical phenomena in Kazakh or Russian, and only then try to comprehend their content in English. On the other hand, these students will be specialists who will be able to teach physics in at least two languages, for example, Kazakh-English or Russian-English.

In the third case, students have the opportunity to work directly with textbooks in English, for example, with books prepared by Oxford University (Oxford University Press) in the library of our Universities. They are fully implemented by the teachers of the Faculty of Physics.

We realized that working with students in the fourth case is very difficult. Such students either do not know physics well, i.e. they did not really study physics at school, or they do not know English well, they were not interested in studying it. Therefore, in accordance with the above features, we believe that it would be effective to teach students separately in small groups.

In particular, teaching physics in English encourages students to discover, conduct various observations and experiments, expanding their vocabulary. The main thing is that their English vocabulary is replenished, conversational skills are formed [2].

To date, there are many innovative technologies that meet the requirements of training. Modern technologies are designed to increase the interest and motivation of students to study.

In Kazakhstan, as in many countries of the world, in recent years, integrated teaching of the subject and English has been carried out using two approaches CLIL and EMI: CLIL (Content Language Integrated Learning) is a combination of content and language didactic methodology, which allows the formation of linguistic and communicative competencies outside the language [4]. Integrated learning, i.e. CLIL, takes into account the importance of forming interdisciplinary connections in the classroom, that is, CLIL technology is considered as a necessary tool for teaching a foreign language in other disciplines.

EMI (English as a Medium of Instruction) is a method of teaching mathematical and engineering disciplines, developed recently [5]. The main idea of EMI is to combine the study of two subjects at once, one of

which is physics (mathematics), and the other is English. However, the difficulty in applying this technique in schools, in addition to the lack of subject teachers with knowledge of English, is the lack of necessary educational and methodological complexes. American or British textbooks cannot always be used, since the language of their writing is difficult for schoolchildren [3].

One of the most popular methods of implementing multilingualism is ESP (English for Specific Purposes). ESP focuses on learning English through the taught subject [6].

Based on the experience accumulated so far, as well as the above methodological features, we decided to make the following specific recommendations.

1. In connection with the above cases, we consider it necessary to develop curricula with specifics for each of them and increase the number of hours of physical disciplines in English (lectures, practices, laboratory work) for the first two groups (Kazakh-English, Russian-English) by one and a half times.

2. If the above proposal is implemented, the question arises of extending the term of study of English-speaking groups. In fact, if we want to train qualified teachers capable of teaching physical disciplines in two languages (Kazakh-English, Russian-English) in accordance with modern requirements, it would be better to extend their training for six months or a year. It will also be important to send students studying in an English group to foreign universities for a few months or even a semester.

If you look at history, examples of the second sentence have already been in the education sector of the country. For example, in the second half of the last century, that is, in Soviet times, at the physics department of the only state university in the Republic of Kazakhstan (Almaty) there was a special group (special group) studying in English. But they studied for a year more than Kazakh and Russian groups, that is, for six years. We know that many of these specialists who studied in these special groups worked fruitfully in the field of education and science during the years of independence. We think this example is also one of the most productive cases where we can take an example.

In conclusion, we hope that the issues raised in our article and the scientific and methodological recommendations made will be useful for our colleagues working in this field.

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